

Occurrence of rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella oryzae* in Portugal

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In Portugal, irrigated rice—mostly cultivar Ringo—is planted on 32,000 ha. The 140,000 t annual production supplies about 2/3 the national consumption. No systematic survey of rice nematodes in the rice area had been conducted.

In 1980, we found specimens of *H. oryzae* (van Breda de Haan, 1902) Luc & Goodey, 1964 in soil samples collected in a vineyard established near a ricefield in central Portugal. In 1986-88, we undertook an exploratory survey covering the main rice-producing areas (see figure).

Ricefields at different sites were sampled at harvest or soon after and 30 root and soil samples per field collected. Each soil sample was composed

Location of ricefields surveyed for rice root nematode in Portugal, 1986-88. Solid circles = nematodes present, open circles = nematodes absent.

of three subsamples collected from around the rice roots, using a soil auger to 25-30 cm deep. Each root sample was composed of all the roots from two rice plants.

Parasitic nematodes were separated from the soil by sugar centrifugal flotation. For nematode extraction, undetached roots were washed free of soil and incubated in tap water for at least a week.

Male, female, and juvenile rice root nematodes whose morphometrics agree with those reported for *H. oryzae* were detected in 50% of the samples (see map). Nematode density ranged from 5 (3 females, 2 juveniles) to 30 (6 females, 3 males, 21 juveniles)/250 ml of soil and was as high as 31 (4 females, 1 male, 26 juveniles)/root sample.

This is the first record of rice root nematode *H. oryzae* in Portugal. None of the seven *Hirschmanniella* species known to attack rice has been reported in European ricefields. □

Population density of nematode *Pratylenchus zaei* at harvest and yield of upland rice UPLRi-5

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Population densities of more than 250 *P. zaei* per liter soil plus 1 g roots have been reported in upland ricefields in the Philippines and other Asian countries.

We studied the relationship between plant-parasitic nematode populations and yield of single hills of rice cultivar UPLRi-5 in an IRRI field naturally infested with *Aulosphora penetrans*, *Criconemella onoensis*, *Helicotylenchus* sp., *Pratylenchus zaei*, and *Tylenchorhynchus annulatus*.

Nematode population densities were determined in the rhizosphere and in the roots of 400 hills randomly selected at harvest. The weight of filled grains of each hill also was measured.

The weight of filled grains was correlated negatively with number of *P. zaei* detected per g roots or per liter soil plus 1 g roots (1 ls + 1 gr).

The table shows yield per hill after grouping the 400 hills into five classes based on population densities of *P. zaei*. Yield differences between hills supporting fewer than 50 *P. zaei* per 1 ls + 1 gr and those supporting 250 to 500 *P. zaei* was 14%; it was 16% between less than 50 and more than 500 *P. zaei* per 1 ls + 1 gr.

Because healthier host plants

Relation between population density of *Pratylenchus zaei* at harvest and average filled grain weight per hill of upland rice cultivar UPLRi-5.

Nematodes (no.)	Hills (no.)	Yield ^a (g)
0-50	77	4.4 a
50-100	54	4.3 abc
100-250	99	4.2 abc
250-500	79	3.8 bc
>500	91	3.7 bc

^a Average yield followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by t-test

support higher multiplication rates of plant-parasitic nematodes, yield is usually poorly correlated with nematode population density at harvest. It is better correlated with initial population density. Nevertheless, these results indicate substantial yield losses associated with *P. zaei* infestations in upland rice. The yield losses may be due to the nematode or to pathogens or stresses associated with the nematode. □

Farming systems

Legume residue incorporation and wetland rice yield

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Punjab soils are generally light in texture and have very low available N